

«THE PECULIARITIES OF POPULAR SCIENCE TEXT WHICH DO NOT OCCUR IN OTHER VARIATIONS»

SAIDOVA MAVJUDA

lecturer of the Department of Practical Course of English Language, Bokhtar State University
of Nosiri Khusrav named after. Tajikistan

Annotation. For the lecture the main pragmatic aims are to educate and to impart information while entertaining is auxiliary and serves for keeping the audience involved and absorbed by the subject. For the popular science text, especially in the case of TV program, the main aim is indeed to entertain. It is supposed that one could evoke the viewers' interest to the informational-didactic content of the text and motivate them to the further studies of the subject. Hence popular science texts, as opposed to lectures, may fail to contain serious data, but focus our attention on the most vivid and fascinating aspects of the subject.

Key words: main pragmatic, impart information, audience, entertain, auxiliary, absorbed, involved, main aim, indeed, didactic, evoke, motivate, subject, opposed, focus, supposed.

Among all variations of the prepared speech popular science text is the most similar to lecture. On one hand, the pragmatic aims of the both variations coincide (to educate, to entertain, to impart information), but on the other, the priority of these aims is absolutely different. For the lecture the main pragmatic aims are to educate and to impart information while entertaining is auxiliary and serves for keeping the audience involved and absorbed by the subject. For the popular science text, especially in the case of TV program, the main aim is indeed to entertain. It is supposed that one could evoke the viewers' interest to the informational-didactic content of the text and motivate them to the further studies of the subject. Hence popular science texts, as opposed to lectures, may fail to contain serious data, but focus our attention on the most vivid and fascinating aspects of the subject.

A popular science style text should have an easily-read structure. It brings about the simplification of the utterance at all linguistic levels. If we compare academic text, presented to the professional audience, and popular science text, we will find the following differences:

Tab. 1

Academic text	Popular science text
Is full of abstract notions	A more simple syntax
Is arranged in a logical pattern	All terms are defined
Extensive use of terms	The sentences are topically divided, phrasal emphasis
Complex sentences with branched syntactic linking prevail	falls at the terminology units
	The length of the syntagmas is reduced and the length of pauses – increased

In addition the text can be often supplied with illustrations and other graphic means. As far as the TV programs are concerned, their format allows to use audio and graphics simultaneously and that results in a radically new quality of data presentation. The details of it would be further revealed in the second chapter of this work, while generally we could only say that this new level provides a deeper interaction between the viewers and the subject in the emotional sphere.

Here we could recollect the words of N.I. Mironova who says that 'A man's emotional state strongly determines his perception, attention and ideation. It is proved that the people pay attention first to the information, the emotional coloring of which corresponds to their own emotional state'.

And to influence the emotional state of a person there is nothing better than proper music background. Indeed, the popular science broadcasts always have a beautiful soundtrack which is carefully fitted to the sequence of key frames and evokes the needed feelings in the viewers. It would

not be a hyperbole to say that none other variation – whether it be lecture or news – requires so extensive, almost obligatory use of soundtrack. For the purpose of the analysis we have chosen two video recordings (total duration of about min). These were two episodes from the BBC popular science films ‘Allergy’ and ‘Animals – The Inside Story’.

As a result of the auditory analysis we have observed the following peculiarities of the popular science texts:

Factual information is logically structured and organized in phonetic paragraphs.

The paragraphs are delimited by a pause. Such pauses are filled only with music.

Music serves to connect parts of the text containing factual information. It may also serve to delimit one part of the text from another. In such cases the music is different.

The combination of music and reading is used to mark the transition from one topic to another. In such cases no new information is given (and the music is combined with the text).

Music is used to enforce the effect of reading.

Important information in the film is accompanied by a loud and a more dynamic music. In such cases the fractional division of the text into parts is different. The reader uses short and abrupt sense-groups. Such a manner of reading in combination with the music creates the atmosphere of tension and helps to involve the audience.

To transfer factual information the video and audio perception channels are involved. Thus, every part of factual information given by the reader is illustrated by a picture.

The reader uses all phonetic means to manage the attention of the audience. Temporal and pitch variations are accompanied by the changes of loudness and voice quality. The most important words are highlighted by the reader. After an overview of modern taxonomy of texts and analyzing the materials offering the clear instances of the object of our research we have succeeded.

Firstly, we have validated that popular science text has particular characteristics that make it different from other variations of prepared speech phonetic style. Its main aim is to entertain; lexically and syntactically it is simpler than lectures or oral presentations of science proper texts; phonetically it is more vivid and casual.

Secondly, we consider it to be an important fact that the prosodic features of popular science text are closely connected with kinetic means of non-verbal communication. Moreover, the use of special background music effects in order to influence the audience and its perception of information might be employed and it is a unique feature not present in other variations of prepared speech.

LITERATURE:

1. Баранов А.Г. «Функционально-прагматическая концепция текста» - монография, М., 1993.
2. Кривнова О.Ф. «Научная речь как объект и материал фонетического исследования» // Труды международной конференции «Функциональные стили звучащей речи» 5-7 сентября 2005 г., Москва, МГУ им. Ломоносова – М., 2005.
3. Кудинова Е.С. «Взаимодействие невербальных и речевых характеристик в процессе коммуникации» // Вестник МГЛУ (580 выпуск) – С. 55-78.
4. Медведева Т.В., Скопинцева Т.С., Степкина И.Ю. «Коммуникативная фонетика: уч. пос. для студентов старших курсов. – 4-е изд. доп. и перераб. – М.: ИПК МГЛУ «Рема», 2010.
5. Миронова Н.И. «Публицистический стиль речи: функция воздействия в свете когнитивных процессов» // Труды международной конференции «Функциональные стили звучащей речи» 5-7 сентября 2005 г., Москва, МГУ им. Ломоносова – М., 2005.